

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS

Title: **Transcriptome analysis of two isolates of the tomato pathogen *Cladosporium fulvum* uncovers genome-wide patterns of alternative splicing events during a host infection cycle.**

Running title: The landscape of alternative splicing in *C. fulvum*

Authors/Affiliations: Alex Z. Zaccaron^{a,b}, Li-Hung Chen^{a,*}, Ioannis Stergiopoulos^{a,#}

^a Department of Plant Pathology, University of California Davis (UCD), Davis, CA, USA.

^b Integrative Genetics and Genomics Graduate Group, University of California, Davis, CA 95616.

* Current address: National Chung Hsing University (NCHU), Taichung, Taiwan.

Correspondence: Ioannis Stergiopoulos: University of California Davis, Department of Plant Pathology, One Shield Avenue, Davis, CA 95616-8751, USA, Tel: +1-530-400-9802, email: istergiopoulos@ucdavis.edu

S1. SUPPLEMENTARY RESULTS

S1.1 RNA sequencing of *C. fulvum* isolates Race 5 and Race 4 during interaction with tomato.

The transcriptomes of *C. fulvum* isolates Race 5 and Race 4 were sequenced at high depth during their interaction with *Solanum lycopersicum* cv. Moneymaker at seven timepoints (2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, and 14 dpi) and from three independent infections (i.e. biological replicates), generating between 65 M and 221 M RNAseq reads per sample (Table S1). As fungal biomass during the early stages of the infection is typically minimal, RNAseq libraries produced from infected tissue samples collected at 2, 4, 6, and 8 dpi were sequenced at higher depth compared to RNAseq libraries corresponding to samples from 10, 12, and 14 dpi (Table S1), thereby increasing the chances of capturing fungal transcripts from early in the infection process. Before RNAseq read mapping, reads were assigned to either the *C. fulvum* isolate Race 5 (1) or the tomato reference genome of cv. Heinz 1706 version SL4.0 (2), using the alignment-free *k*-mer method implemented in the *seal.sh* script from the BMap package (Table S2). Reads matching the tomato genome were removed and the remaining reads were mapped to the *C. fulvum* genome. As expected, at early timepoints, the percentage of reads mapping to the *C. fulvum* genome was considerably low (Table 1). Specifically, at 2 dpi and 4 dpi, between 135,953 (0.08%) and 437,311 (0.21%) of the reads obtained from tomato leaf samples infected with *C. fulvum* Race 5, and between 409,880 (0.23%) and 1,852,149 (0.92%) of the reads from tomato leaf samples infected with *C. fulvum* Race 4 mapped to the *C. fulvum* Race 5 genome. However, the percentage of reads that successfully mapped to the *C. fulvum* genome significantly increased from samples collected at later timepoints, reaching between 27.1 M (32.55%) and 37.6 M (43.87%) for isolate Race 5, and between 12.7 M (19.5%) and 45.7 M (57.64%) reads for isolate Race 4 at 12 dpi and 14 dpi, respectively (Table 1).

S1.2 Isolates Race 5 and Race 4 of *C. fulvum* share nearly all their intron splice sites.

Intron-containing genes may undergo alternative splicing (AS), thereby generating diverse mRNA isoforms. A total 9,356 and 9,278 intron-containing genes have been reported in the genomes of isolates Race 5 and Race 4, respectively (3) (Table S3). As introns are spliced by spliceosomes at conserved sequences, a splice site analysis was first performed to determine the extent to which intron splice sites were conserved between orthologous genes in the two isolates. To start the analysis, we first investigate whether the introns that were predicted in the genes of *C. fulvum* isolates Race 5 and Race 4 (3) were supported by the RNAseq data generated in this study, by mapping the reads to the genomes of the two isolates. Ensuing splice site analysis revealed that from the 17,029 and 16,842 introns predicted in the genes of isolates Race 5 and Race 4, 13,639 (80.1%) and 12,718 (75.5%) could be confirmed with at least five RNAseq reads, respectively. Moreover, from the 9,356 and 9,278 intron-containing genes in isolates Race 5 and Race 4, 7,769 (83.0%) and 7,284 (78.5%) had at least one of their introns confirmed, and 5,309 (56.7%) and 4,453 (48.0%) had all their introns confirmed, respectively. This indicated that the predicted exon-intron structures in the intron-containing genes of isolates Race 5 and Race 4 were well-supported by the RNAseq data.

To further investigate whether orthologous genes in isolates Race 5 and Race 4 had similar number and size of introns, a total of 14,747 one-to-one ortholog gene pairs were analyzed. These ortholog pairs were obtained with OrthoFinder (4), and included 98.4% and 99.0% of all predicted genes in isolates Race 5 ($n=$

14,993) and Race 4 ($n= 14,895$), respectively. From the 14,747 ortholog gene pairs, 14,739 (99.9%) pairs had the same number of introns in both orthologous genes (Fig 1A) and 14,648 (99.3%) pairs had the same total size of intronic sequences (Fig 1B), thereby indicating a high conservation in the number and size of introns between the two isolates.

Finally, we investigated whether orthologous genes between the two isolates also shared the same start and end coordinates of their introns. To do so, the gene annotation of isolate Race 4 was mapped to the genome of Race 5 using LiftOff, thereby resulting in a new annotation for isolate Race 4 but with its gene coordinates now modeled on the genome of Race 5. This enabled intron coordinates to be compared between pairs of ortholog genes, which revealed that from the 14,747 one-to-one gene orthologs between isolate Race 5 and Race 4, 14,729 (99.9%) had the same number of introns with the same start and end coordinates, and only 18 ortholog pairs had different number of introns or intron coordinates. These results indicated that splicing sites and intron coordinates are highly conserved between the two *C. fulvum* isolates.

S1.3 Transcriptome profiling of *C. fulvum* during host infections reveals extensive transcript isoform heterogeneity among isolates and infections.

The RNAseq reads that were obtained in this study for the two isolates were then used to perform reference-based transcriptome assemblies, using the genome of isolate Race 5 (1) as reference. However, preliminary attempts indicated the presence of chimeric transcripts in the data, which possibly resulted from overlapping untranslated regions of physically close neighboring genes (Fig S1). Therefore, transcripts were instead assembled in a gene-by-gene strategy, in which reads that mapped to the genes of each isolate were first extracted and then used to assemble the unique transcript isoforms that originated from each individual gene. Using these reads, a total of 612,075 transcripts could be assembled from reads mapping to the genes of the two isolates across all timepoints and infection replicates (Table S4). However, many of the transcripts were assembled multiple times among the samples, indicating that they were redundant. To obtain a set of unique transcripts, all the 612,075 assembled transcripts were next clustered such that identical or fully contained sequences (i.e. a sequence within a sequence) were clustered together, and the longest sequence from each cluster was chosen as the representative. In doing so, a total of 57,148 clusters were generated, each of which represented a putative unique transcript isoform.

SUPPLEMENTARY REFERENCES

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S2. SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURES

FIG S1. Preliminary transcriptome assembly generated chimeric transcripts spanning genes physically close in the genome. The figure shows a region of 16 kb in chromosome 1 of *Cladosporium fulvum* Race 5 containing six predicted genes. RNA-seq coverage of reads from the first of the three infections that were performed (i.e. biological replicate 1) at 14 dpi during interaction with tomato is shown above the predicted genes. Reference-based transcriptome assembly based on the reads shown resulted in chimeric transcripts, shown in red, that span multiple genes.

FIG S2. A high heterogeneity in transcripts produced by *Cladosporium fulvum* isolates Race 5 and Race 4 during tomato infections is seen between the two isolates and the three different infections that were performed with each isolate. (A) The total number of transcripts that are shared between isolates Race 5 and Race 4. The Venn diagram shows all uniquely assembled transcripts, after combining all transcripts assembled across three independent tomato infections (i.e. biological replicates) and the seven timepoints sampled in each infection. (B) The total number of assembled transcripts shared by all biological replicates (Rep. 1, Rep. 2, and Rep. 3) for isolates Race 5 and Race 4. The Venn diagrams show all unique transcripts assembled for each infection and isolate, after combining the assembled transcripts from all seven sampled timepoints during the infection. Darker colors of intersections indicate higher numbers.

FIG S3. An overall low number of transcripts are constitutively present in all three tomato infections performed either with *Cladosporium fulvum* isolates Race 5 or Race 4 and in every of the seven infection timepoints that were sampled. Venn diagrams showing the number of transcripts supported by one, two, or all three biological replicates (Rep. 1, Rep. 2, and Rep. 3) at each sampled timepoint (2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, and 14 dpi) for isolates Race 5 and Race 4. A biological replicate represents a different infection experiment with isolates Race 5 and Race 4. Darker colors of intersections indicate higher numbers. To identify transcripts supported by each replicate, all assembled transcripts were organized into clusters, such that each cluster contained identical or fully contained transcripts, and thus each cluster represented a unique transcript. A transcript is considered supported by all three replicates if the corresponding cluster contained transcripts assembled from all three replicates.

FIG S4. The number of transcripts shared by *Cladosporium fulvum* isolates Race 5 and Race 4 increases when singleton transcripts that could not be reproduced between infections were filtered out. (A) The total number of transcripts shared between isolates Race 5 and Race 4. The Venn diagram shows all uniquely assembled transcripts after combining all transcripts assembled across the sampled timepoints and infections (i.e. biological replicates), and subsequently removing singleton transcripts that were present in only one sample, i.e., present in only one replicate, in one timepoint, for one isolate. (B) The total number of assembled transcripts shared among biological replicates (Rep. 1, Rep. 2, and Rep. 3) for isolates Race 5 and Race 4. The Venn diagrams show all unique transcripts assembled for each replicate after combining all timepoints and removing transcripts that were present in only one sample. Darker colors of intersections indicate higher numbers.

FIG S5. The number of transcripts common in all three tomato infections performed either with *Cladosporium fulvum* isolates Race 5 or Race 4 and in each of the seven sampled infection timepoints, after filtering out singleton transcripts that were present in only one sample. Venn diagrams showing the number of transcripts supported by one, two, or all three biological replicates (Rep. 1, Rep. 2, and Rep. 3) at each timepoint (2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, and 14 dpi) for isolates Race 5 and Race 4 after removing transcripts that were present in only one sample, i.e., present in only one replicate, in one timepoint, for one isolate. Darker colors of intersections indicate higher numbers.

FIG S6. The distribution of genes predicted to undergo alternative splicing (AS) recurrently in the genomes of *Cladosporium fulvum* isolates Race 5 and Race 4 during tomato infections. Circos plot showing the chromosomes of the reference genome of isolate Race 5. The two outermost tracks show the gene and repetitive DNA content, respectively. The predicted locations of centromeres are indicated with white rectangles on the outermost axis. The histograms in the two innermost tracks represent the number of AS genes (0 to 13) along the chromosomes for isolates Race 5 and Race 4. Numbers in all tracks were calculated using a sliding window of 30 kb.

FIG S7. The upstream regions of genes predicted to undergo alternative splicing (AS) in the genomes of *Cladosporium fulvum* isolates Race 5 and Race 4 during tomato infections, have higher amounts of repetitive DNA than genes with no evidence of AS. The violin plots show the distribution of the amount of repetitive DNA (i.e., predicted transposable elements) present in the up- and downstream intergenic regions of genes with and without evidence of AS in the genomes of isolates Race 5 and Race 4. The figure shows that the repetitive DNA content of upstream intergenic regions of AS genes in Race 5 (average= 6.26%) is significantly larger compared to the genes with no evidence of AS (average= 5.5%). Similar significance level were observed for upstream intergenic regions of genes from Race 4 with evidence of AS (average= 6.13%) and with no evidence of AS (average= 5.59%). In contrast, no significant differences of amount of repetitive DNA in the downstream intergenic regions of AS genes (Race 5 average= 5.19%; Race 4 average = 5.23%) compared to genes with no evidence of AS (Race 5 average = 4.96%; Race 4 average = 4.94%). The p-values were obtained with the Wilcoxon rank sum test.

FIG S8. Alternative splicing (AS) events in effector-encoding genes of *Cladosporium fulvum* isolates Race 5 and Race 4. The figure shows AS events identified in the *Ecp1*, *Ecp5*, *Ecp6*, and *Ecp12* effector-encoding genes. In all cases, AS altered the coding sequence of the genes, and the AS events were conserved between the two isolates. In *Ecp1*, an alternative 5' splice site (A5) event results in frameshift. In *Ecp5*, an intro retention (IR) event results in the modification of the 17 amino acids after the splice site. In *Ecp6*, an alternative 5' splice site (A5) event results in the modification of 6 amino acids after the splice site. In *Ecp12*, an alternative 3' splice site (A3) event results in the modification of 2 amino acids after the splice site.

FIG S9. Two genes encoding putative transcription factors in *Cladosporium fulvum* isolates Race 5 and Race 4, and their predicted protein isoforms produced via alternative splicing (AS) events. (A) AS in gene *CLAFUR5_09583* leads to 10 different protein isoforms in both isolates Race 5 and Race 4. (B) AS in gene *CLAFUR5_09979* leads to 13 different protein isoforms in both isolates Race 5 and Race 4. The number on the left-hand side counts the number of distinct protein isoforms produced via AS by each gene in each isolate. Image is exported from IGV. Thick rectangles represent coding sequences, whereas thinner rectangles represent untranslated regions, and lines represent introns.

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FIG S10. Genes from *Cladosporium fulvum* isolate Race 5 with significant evidence of differential isoform usage at the transcript level during disease progression, which are common to both isolates. The line graphs show 17 AS genes from isolate Race 5 that produce transcripts whose relative abundance significantly changes during the infection. In the line graphs, the points represent the expression values in TPM (transcripts per million) of the individual transcripts across different timepoints of the infection. Standard deviation in the TPM values from three infections (i.e. biological replicates) is shown as vertical lines. The trends of transcript expression across time are shown as thick lines connecting the average TPM values for each individual transcript.

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FIG S11. Genes from *Cladosporium fulvum* isolate Race 4 with significant evidence of differential isoform usage at the transcript level during disease progression, which are common to both isolates. The line graphs show 17 AS genes from isolate Race 4 that produce transcripts whose relative abundance significantly changes during the infection. In the line graphs, the points represent the expression values in TPM (transcripts per million) of the individual transcripts across different timepoints of the infection. Standard deviation in the TPM values from three infections (i.e. biological replicates) is shown as vertical lines. The trends of transcript expression across time are shown